

Sociodemographic and Clinical Profile of Patients with Irritable Bowel Syndrome

Srikanth¹, Vasanthi², Rama Chandra Reddy³

¹MBBS, MD Internal Medicine, Warangal Hospital and Diagnostic Centre, Warangal

²MBBS, MD Internal Medicine, Aditya Hospital,

³MBBS, MD Emergency Medicine, 2nd year PG student, MS Ramaiah Medical College, Bangalore, Karnataka

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Srikanth

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Abstract:

Introduction: Irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) is one of the most common gastrointestinal illnesses, characterized by non-specific symptoms such as abdominal pain and abnormal bowel habits but no recognized organic cause. Its prevalence varies between communities. The current study was conducted to determine the sociodemographic and clinical profile among patients with IBS.

Materials and Methods: A cross sectional retrospective was done at Warangal hospital and diagnostic centre, Warangal during the period from December 2021 to December 2023. Age, gender, Place of residence, education and occupation level, socioeconomic status as classified using Kuppuswamy scale, lifestyle habits (smoking, alcohol consumption) were assessed as part of sociodemographic profile. Clinical profile of patients included presence of Intestinal and extra-intestinal symptoms, and signs.

Results: Fifty patients were part of this study. The mean age of the patients was 42.6 ± 18.3 years, ranging from 12 to 72 years. 35 (70%) patients were males & 15 (30%) patients were females. The majority 28 (56%) patients belong to the age group of 30-45 years. The majority 27 (65.9%) patients belonged to rural areas. Majority 15 (30%) patients had primary education. A large proportion of the patients 18 (36%) were unemployed. Most of the patients 17 (34%) were upper lower class. Most of the patients were non-smokers and non-alcoholics. The most frequent presenting symptoms were abdominal pain (60%), constipation (58%) and diarrhoea (40%).

Conclusion: IBS is a public health issue that lowers the quality of life for individuals affected. The most common presenting symptoms were abdominal discomfort and constipation. Various mental health problems and psychosomatic disorders must be screened and treated as part of the management process.

Keywords: Irritable Bowel Syndrome, Abdominal Pain, Clinical Features.

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Introduction

Irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) is the most prevalent functional gastrointestinal condition in clinical practice. [1] Irritable bowel syndrome has received a lot of attention in the healthcare profession over the last two decades because of its increasing prevalence, often devastating symptoms, and variable symptom depiction. IBS is characterized by chronic digestive symptoms such as abdominal discomfort, bloating, constipation, diarrhea, or a combination of these, without obvious intestinal lesions [2-3]. The Rome IV criteria, developed by a worldwide group of experts in gut-brain connection disorders, can be used to diagnose IBS and conduct research [4].

Because of the community's poor health-seeking behaviour and the difficulty encountered by medical practitioners in diagnosing IBS, it remains an underdiagnosed gastrointestinal condition [5].

On average, it takes up to four years to get a diagnosis [6]. The stigma connected with this disease makes it even more difficult for individuals to obtain treatment and assistance [6].

Although the etiology is unknown, various physical and psychological elements have been identified as contributing to its pathogenesis, including stress, worry, and aberrant attitudes toward the disease, all of which worsen patients' symptoms [7,8]. This study was conducted to investigate the sociodemographic and clinical profile of people with IBS.

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional retrospective study was conducted at Warangal Hospital and Diagnostic Center, Warangal, between December 2021 and December 2023. After approval was obtained from

the medical superintendent of the hospital, medical records of in-patients diagnosed with IBS were reviewed, This study includes people diagnosed with IBS depending on ROME IV criteria between December 2021 and December 2023. Excluded were those diagnosed with IBS based on different criteria. A semi-structured proforma was used for data collection.

Assessed as part of sociodemographic profile were age, gender, place of residence, education and occupation level, socioeconomic position as defined using Kuppaswamy scale [9,10] lifestyle habits (smoking, alcohol intake). Patients' clinical profile comprised intestinal and extra-intestinal symptoms and signs.

Data were entered and analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.

Descriptive statistics were presented as frequencies and percentages,

Results

Fifty patients were part of this study. The mean age of the patients was 42.6 ± 18.3 years, ranging from 12 to 72 years. 35 (70%) patients were males & 15 (30%) patients were females.

The majority 28 (56%) patients belong to the age group of 30-45 years. The majority 27 (65.9%) patients belonged to rural areas.

Majority 15 (30%) patients had primary education. A large proportion of the patients 18 (36%) were unemployed. Most of the patients 17 (34%) were upper lower class. Most of the patients were non-smokers and non-alcoholics (Table 1)

Table 1: Demographic and personal characteristics of patients

Parameter	No. of patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
<30	6	12
30-45	28	56
>45 years	16	32
Gender		
Male	35	70
Female	15	30
Residence		
Urban	19	38
Rural	31	62
Education		
Primary	15	30
Secondary	12	24
College	9	18
Graduation	9	18
Post-graduation or above	3	6
Illiterate	2	4
Occupation		
Professionals	9	18
Skilled	10	20
Semi-skilled	4	8
Unemployed	18	36
Students	5	10
Housewives	4	8
Socioeconomic status		
Lower class	5	10
Upper lower class	17	34
Lower middle class	14	28
Upper middle class	12	24
Upper class	2	4
Smoking		
Yes	13	26
No	37	74
Alcohol intake		
Yes	10	20
No	40	80

The most frequent presenting symptoms were abdominal pain (60%), constipation (58%) and diarrhoea (40%). other extra intestinal symptoms were Anxiety, Depression, Headache & bodyache. The signs observed were Presence of mucus in stool, Presence of blood in stool & Abdominal distension (Table 2).

Table 2: Clinical presentation of IBS among the patients

Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Abdominal pain	30	60
constipation	29	58
Diarrhoea	20	40
Reduced appetite	15	30
Flatulence	5	10
Bloating	16	32
headache	9	18
backache	5	10
anxiety	12	24
depression	9	18
Presence of mucus in stool	28	56
Presence of blood in stool	10	20
Abdominal distension	6	12

Discussion

IBS is more common worldwide in women than in men. [11, 12] But in India, more males than women are afflicted by IBS, with a prevalence between 66% and 87%. [13] Our findings match those of earlier research from India with a larger preponderance in men (70%).

Our gender distribution results thus reflect those of other Indian studies. ([14] In this study most common IBS patients were middle aged. Previous studies revealed the highest IBS incidence in those between the ages of 45 and 64. [15] other study revealed that Similar frequency exists among young, middle-aged, and elderly persons. [16] According to Asian criteria, abdominal pain or discomfort is the most common symptom of IBS. [17] In our study, a high proportion of patients (60%) reported abdominal pain as the most common symptom of IBS.

Stress is thought to change enteric nervous system function by means of hormones and neurotransmitters, thereby inducing IBS. Singh et al. proposed that neurotransmitters and hormones (serotonin and monoamine oxidase) may have a role in exacerbating psychiatric symptoms in IBS patients. [18] Psychiatric disorders range in frequency in IBS from 40% to 100%. [19] Tilburg et al. investigated the psychological elements most influencing IBS severity and came to the indirect influence of anxiety on amplification of IBS symptoms. [20]

Other studies also showed people with IBS more anxiety and depression than in healthy controls. [21–23] Mikocka-Walus et al. found that anxiety and depression were prevalent in 57% and 15% of IBS patients, respectively. [24] In the current study, we found that a small proportion of IBS patients had anxiety (24%) and sadness (18%).

Conclusion

IBS is a public health issue that lowers the quality of life for individuals affected. The most common presenting symptoms were abdominal discomfort and constipation.

Various mental health problems and psychosomatic disorders must be screened and treated as part of the management process.

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